

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGIC FEATURES OF THE MEANS OF REALIZATION OF THE SEMANTICS OF “LIFE” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. *This article deals with the data related to the linguoculturologic features of the means of realization of the semantics of “life”.*

Key words: *linguistics, culture, linguoculturology, linguocultural*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ СРЕДСТВ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ СЕМАНТИКИ «ЖИЗНЬ» В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *В статье приводятся данные, касающиеся лингвокультурологических особенностей средств реализации семантики «жизнь».*

Ключевые слова: *языкознание, культура, лингвокультурология, лингвокультурология.*

INTRODUCTION

Linguoculturology is one of the main aspects of linguistic investigations, it deals with various issues that relate with language spirit and cultural variation of a nation, encompasses various national cultural notions and theories of conversational structure.

This branch studies national spirit that is reflected in a language. It is associated with other studies as philosophy, logics, sociology, anthropology and semantics; and covers national-cultural knowledge through speech communication. The appearance of linguocultural study considerably depends on the development of philosophic and linguistic theories during the XIX-XX centuries. In the last century, a number of research works were maintained in Russia. One of the well-known book belongs to V.A. Maslova called Introduction to linguoculturology[1]. The author defines research fields and methodological basis of contemporary linguoculturology deeply in her book. Her hypothesis are valuable to be applied in nowadays' new investigations not only about linguocultural problems, and also in other linguistic and philosophic branches. Scientists that link to this linguistic branch make a great deal of investigations. V.N. Teliya writes that methodological basis of linguoculturology serves “semiotic presentation indications of this interaction, considered as cognitive contents of mental procedures, the result of which is cultural licalization of mental structures”[2] . According to this idea, linguocultural study is not isolated from other scientific branches. As it is a linguistic field it assists to the other branches of language learning and develop with the help of them. In the book of Uzbek linguist U.K. Yusupov “Contrastive linguistics of the English and Uzbek languages” it is clearly mentioned that linguocultureme is a linguistic or speech unit defining one part of a culture; consequently linguoculturology is a branch of linguistics, which studies interrelation between language and culture, and conveying culture in a language [3] Still it is clarified that linguoculturology focuses attention onto the reflection of spiritual state in the language of a human in the society. In general, this branch analyses cultural colours of linguistic units as well as it studies language through culture. Besides, linguoculturology possesses a number of following specific features: 1) it is a subject of synthetic type, occupying bordering position between science and, learners of

culture and philology; 2) the main object of culturology is interrelation of language and culture and interpretation of this interaction; 3) as the subject of investigation of linguoculturology serves spiritual and material culture, verbalized artefacts, forming “the language picture of the world”; 4) linguoculturology is oriented to the new system of cultural values, put forth by the modern life in the society, to the objective information on the cultural life of the country. Each subject or a branch of subject owns its studying object. The term “cultureme” (or “linguocultureme”) is admitted to be used in scientific researches for naming the object of linguoculturology.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The difference between cultureme and lexeme is recognized in its definition: cultureme is a word, phrase or even a full sentence in a language, which embraces national, social or mental peculiarities that are specific to the culture of the language. Some scholars successfully distinguish subtypes of one language according to the types of culture layers: 1) literary language – elite culture; 2) popular language – “the third culture”; 3) dialects and sayings – popular culture; 4) argot (words and expressions which are used by small groups of people and which are not easily understood by other people) – traditional-professional culture. In this paper, the attention is focused to the contrastive study of proverbs that stay in the third component of this classification. It is obvious that appearing and forming of linguocultural aspect of the concept “life”, besides, admitting them into live conversations by the nation takes sometimes considerably long period of time. The English and Uzbek languages are believed to have long history. English has background that comes from the Latin language, therefore a huge number of English paremiologic stock have Latin bases; some of them are identical to the historical forms, some of them faced to changes in comparison with the old ones. Through many years, other languages have been affecting to the English language, too. As a result, some proverbs are often borrowed from them in the way of translating linguocultural aspect of the concept “life”, into English as well. W. Mieder introduces the four major sources four common European proverbs, including English, namely the Greek and the Roman Antiquity, the Bible, the Medieval Latin and the loan translations.[5]

The Uzbek language possesses also long background. It is true that this language was given the name of “Uzbek language” recently, but this language has existed since approximately X-XI century. A huge number of proverbs, sayings and aphorisms are considered as a great wealth of the Uzbek culture. The main sources may be classified as followings: some characters from religious sources and the borrowed translations (mainly from the Arab, Tadjik, Persian and languages). Moreover, there are some proverbs that come from sayings created by the mass media (TV, radio or social nets), expressions of films and songs, and even advertising slogans in all languages including English and Uzbek. However, they need some time to become or to form new proverbs as well.

RESEARCH RESULTS

This article aims to analyse linguo-cultural features of linguocultural aspect of the concept , in these two languages with the help of examples about life. The concept of “life” is an abstract notion which is valuable in a human life that take place in the row of social concepts as “family”, “health”, “wealth” and “labour”. Translating linguocultural aspect of the concept “life”, word-by-word is not sufficient way to express the meaning of concept “life” in the other languages because of culturemes that exists in its content in a target language. It may cause to

misunderstand the basic meaning of a proverb. Therefore, the method of finding equivalents of proverbs in English and Uzbek is used to investigate peculiarities of linguocultural aspect of the concept “life”, in these languages.

A language reflects the particular culture of its nation in reflecting national features and culture of this nation is considerable. Not only traditions of the people and national notions, but also historical places, outstanding people and famous characters of the nation are expressed in the concept ‘life’.

The syntactic and features of the concept “Life” and its relations with other words especially grammatical characters such as which indicates the nouns are articles, adjective participle, number, gerund, demonstrative pronouns, indefinite pronouns and possessive pronouns.

For example: The next life (охират), a long life (узoқ умр), early life (болалик), adult life (балoғат даври), in later life (турмушнинг сўнги йиллири), city life (шахар ҳаёти), village life (қишлоқ ҳаёти), prison life (қамoқдаги ҳаёт), married life (турмушдан кейинги ҳаёт), see life (ҳаётни аччиғини биладиган), a happy life (бахтли турмуш), a normal life (меёрдаги турмуш), a hard life (oғир турмуш). etc.

The word “lifeless” is translated into Uzbek “Турмушсиз” usually determines with lexical units. In comparable languages the concept “**турмуш**” represents a number of communicative pragmatic meanings. In such cases, different levels of language are used and they may form a separate. So, such concept may be used in semantic field of the language.

The concept ‘Life’ means in Uzbek language such words and phrases: турмуш қурди, яшади, умр кўрди, дунё юзини кўрди, дунёга келди, ҳаётни бошидан ўтказди, саксон ёшни қоралади, турмуш кечирди, етмиш ёшни босиб ўтди. In English: came into the world (дунёга келди) to arrive (туғилмоқ), to go through life (турмуш кечирмоқ), to be born (туғилмоқ) and etc.

Besides that the concept “**Турмуш**” may be used in the sentences or sentenceme;

1. У урушда ҳаётини қурбон қилди; 2) расмини ҳаётий чизиш керак; 3) бу ҳаёт – мамот масаласи.

In English;

1. He laid down his life during the war;
- 2) You should draw from life;
- 3) A book that brings the subject to life. (китоб турмушни қизиқарли қилади)
- 4) You should expect him to get life for such a serious crim ; (сиз уни бунақанги жиддий жинояти учун ўлим жазосига ҳукм қилинишини кутган бўлсангиз керак).

Life begins at forty. (турмуш 40 ёшдан бошланади); life goes on. (турмуш давом этади); life is too shot. (ҳаёт жуда қисқа); she is a woman in my life (у мени турмуш ўртоғим); not on my life (асло); such is life (турмуш шунақа); this is the life (мана бунини турмуш деса бўлади).

In the given sentences above shows that, sentenceme usually consists of some words, they may represent a meaning .

Famous English writer William Shakespeare described the concept of “life” in such way; “Кўриш ва сезиш, бу мавжуд бўлмоқликдир, мулоҳаза юритиш эса яшаш демакдир”.

Of course, the people see the life through their view, touching and breathing. The concept of “life’ may be used with lexical units and it may represent different meanings

The concept of “life” may be used in such ways:

For example:

A) The concept of “life” may be used with compound words in English;

Lifebelt, lifeblood, life boy, lifeguard, lifejacket, lifeline, lifesaver, lifespan (умр), lifetime.

B) Using with syntactic units;

1) to spend the life; 2) risk smbs life; 3) put smbs life at risk; 4)lose a life; 5) to get life; 6) to bring smbs to life; 7) get a life; 8) to lay down smbs life; 9) to risk life and limb; 10) to take smbs life; 11) to take smbs own life;[5]

In Uzbek Language: 1) турмушини ўтказмоқ; 3) турмушини хавф остига қўймоқ; 4)қўлдан бой бермоқ(ўйинни); 5) ўлим жазосини олмоқ; 6) қимнидир ҳаётга қайтармоқ; 7) зериктирмоқ, жонга тегмоқ; 8) турмушини қурбон қилмоқ; 9) жонини фидо қилмоқ; 10) қимнидир жонини олмоқ 11) ўз турмушини бузмоқ.

In comparing languages the analyses expressed the concept of “Life” may be used with a number of communicative-pragmatic meanings. In such cases, different means of language are used and they form a separate system of the English language.

During our research we turned into Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language (Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати) the meaning of the word “**Турмуш**” 1 инсоннинг, миллат ва халқнинг яшаш, кун кечириш тарзи, кундалик ҳаёти. *Ёрқин турмуш. Фаравон турмуш кечирмоқ.Яшиш ишласак, ўз турмушимиз фаравон, брт обод бўлади. Ойбек.о.в.шабадалар. Турмуш қаттиқчилигини таътиб пишган Ботирали дунёда мўжиза бўлмаслигини яхши билади. Ҳ.Ғулом, Машғал. Ўрмондаги турмушни ўз кўзинг билан кўриб турибсан.Ҳар бир қултум сув, ҳар бир бурда нон ҳисобли.И.Раҳим, Чин муҳаббат.Умарали қисқа вақт ичида ўз ҳаётида юз берган ўзгаришларни эслади, кейин Ғозининг бетайин турмушини кўз олдига келтирди. И. Раҳим, Ихлос.*

2. Бирор халқ, ижтимоий гуруҳ ва ш.кга хос ҳаёт тарзи, урф-одатлар, расм таомиллар мажмуи. Янги турмуш. *Гавҳарнинг қаришида, боя ўзи ўйлагандек, олифта кийинини яхши кўрадиган қиз эмас, кўпни кўрган, турмушининг пасти-баланд сўқмоқларидан ўтиб келган инсон ўтирар эди.Ў.Ҳошимов, Қалбингга қулоқ сол. Айб сизда ҳам эмас, эски турмушда. Эски турмушда хотинлар ҳар қанақа эркакдан тортинади, эркалар ҳар қанақа хотинга тегишигиси келади. А.Қаҳҳор, Қўшчинор чироқлари.*

3.Жамиятнинг оддий ҳаёт шарт-шароитлари мажмуи, объектив реаллик. *Турмуш онгни белгилайди. Қонунни турмушга сингдириб юборувчи асосий куч бизнинг ўқитувчиларимиздир. Газетадан.*

4. Никоҳ асосида юзага келадиган ҳаёт, эр-хотинлик ҳолати, шу ҳолатдаги ҳаёти. *Бегимхоннинг кўз олдига харита эмас, Эрали жонланди. Қандай тотлт эди, уларнинг турмуши! И.Раҳим, Чин муҳаббат. У турмуши омонот эканини, қачондир оиласи бузулишини кўндан кўнгли сезиб юрар, аммо бунчалик шарманда бўлишни ўйламаган эди. Ў.Ҳошимов, Қалбингга қулоқ сол.*

Турмуши бузилмоқ. *Эр-хотинлик ҳолати ва шу ҳолатдаги ҳаёт барҳам топмоқ. Агар шундай ташлаб қўйила берса...ўртага совуқчилик тушади, оқибатда турмушлари бузилади. Р.Файзий, Чўлга баҳор келди.*

Турмуш ўртоғи Эр-хотинлик ҳолатидаги шахснинг ҳар бири(эр ва хотин бир-бирига нисбатан) *Рустам уйига ширакайф келди. Бироздан сўнг турмуш ўртоғи Шохиста*

ҳам ишдан қайтди. Газетадан. **Турмуш қилмоқ** 1) айн. **турмушга чиқмоқ**. Шу бола ўқинмасин деб турмуш қурмадим, нон заводига кириб ишлаб, ўғлимни ўқитишга киришдим.”Муштум” 2) эр-хотинлик ҳолатида яшамок. *Йигирма йил турмуш қилиб, бола кўрмадим.* И.Рахим, Чин муҳаббат. *Бироқ найранғбоз Абдувоҳид Хурихон Саттарова билан ҳам силлиққина турмуш қилиб кета қолмади.* Муштум. **Турмуш қурмоқ**. к.турмуш қилмоқ. *Она шўрлик йигирма икки ёшида бева қолиб, шу-шу турмуш қурмади.* Ў.Усмонов, Сирли соҳил. *Турмуш қурганига уч йил бўлибди-ю, ҳамон бу уйга кўникиб кетолмайди.* Газетадан. **Турмушга чиқмоқ** Эркак билан оила қурмоқ; эрга текмоқ. *Қизларнинг эрки ўзида севиб, синашиб турмушга чиқишади.*”Гулдаста” *Тўртинчи синфга ўтганимда, онам ўзи билан мактабда ишлайдиган ўқитувчига турмушга чиқди.*Ў.Ҳошимов, Қалбингга кулоқ сол[5].

DISCUSSION

In English the concept “life” from the dictionary Oxford dictionary means[6]:

1. The ability to breathe, grow, reproduce, etc. that people, animals, and plants have before they die and that objects do not have *life and death*. *The body was cold and showed **no signs of life**.* *My father died last year—I wish I could bring him **back to life**.* *In spring the countryside bursts into life.*
2. The state of being alive as a human; an individual person's existence. *The floods caused a massive **loss of life*** (= many people were killed). *He **risked his life** to save his daughter from the fire.* *Hundreds of lives were threatened when the building collapsed.* *The operation **saved her life**.* *My grandfather **lost his life*** (= was killed) *in the war.* *Several attempts have been made on the President's life* (= several people have tried to kill him).
3. Living things ***plant/animal life marine/pond life*** *Is there intelligent life on other planets ?*
4. The period between someone's birth and their death; a part of this period *He's lived here **all his life*** .*I've lived in Iowa for most of my life.**to have a **long/short life*** *He became very weak toward the end of his life.* *Brenda took up tennis **late in life*** *He will spend **the rest of his life*** (= until he dies) *in a wheelchair.* *There's no such thing as a job **for life** any longer.* *She is a **life member** of the club.**in **early/adult life***
5. (used with an adjective) a period of someone's life when they are in a particular situation or job *She has been an accountant all her **working life**.* *He met a lot of interesting people during his life as a student.* *They were very happy throughout their **married life**.*
6. The period of time when something exists or functions *That building **started life** as a drugstore.* *They could see that the company had a limited life* (= it was going to close). *In Italy the average life of a government is eleven months*
7. The punishment of being sent to prison for life; life imprisonment *The judge **gave him life**.* *She is **doing life** for murder*
8. The experience and activities that are typical of all people's existences the worries of everyday life. *He is young and has little **experience of life**.* *Commuting is a part of **daily life** for many people.* *Jill wants to travel and see life for herself.* *We bought a dishwasher **to make life easier**.* *In Africa life can be hard.* *In **real life*** (= when she met him) *he wasn't how she had imagined him at all.* *Life can be difficult when you move to a new town.* *Life isn't like in the movies, you know.*
9. the activities and experiences that are typical of a particular way of living **country/city life** *She enjoyed political life.* **family/married life** *How do you find life in Japan?*

10. A person's experiences during their life; the activities that form a particular part of a person's life He has had **a good life**. **a hard/an easy life** My **day-to-day life** is not very exciting. **a life of luxury**. Her **daily life** involved meeting lots of people. She lived a quiet life in the countryside. Many of these children have led very **sheltered lives** (= they have not had many different experiences). They emigrated to **start a new life** in Canada. He doesn't like to talk about his **private life**. She has a full **social life**. articles about the **love lives** of the stars

11. The quality of being active and exciting **VITALITY** This is a great vacation resort that is **full of life**. in art

12. A living model or a real object or scene that people draw or paint She had lessons in drawing from life. **a life class** (= one in which art students draw a naked man or woman)

13. A story of someone's life She wrote a life of Mozart. in children's games

14. One of a set number of chances before a player is out of a game He's lost two lives, so he's only got one left.

be somebody's life- be the most important person or thing to someone

My children are my life. Writing is his life.

breathe (new) life into something to improve something by introducing new ideas and making people more interested in it The results of their research have breathed new life into the debate.

the breath of life to/for somebody (literary) an essential part of a person's existence Playing the violin has been the breath of life to her for over 20 years.

bring somebody/something to life to make someone or something more interesting or exciting The new teacher really brought French to life for us. Flowers can bring a dull room back to life.

come to life 1. to become more interesting, exciting, or full of activity The game finally came to life in the final quarter. **2.** to start to act or move as if alive In my dream all my toys came to life.

depart this life- to die. People say 'depart this life' to avoid saying 'die.'

a dog's life- an unhappy life, full of problems or unfair treatment He led poor Amy a dog's life. She was desperately lonely, poor dear.

end your days/life (in something)- to spend the last part of your life in a particular state or place He ended his days in poverty.

a fact of life- a situation that cannot be changed, especially one that is unpleasant It's a fact of life that some people will always be racist.

the facts of life- the details about sex and about how babies are born, especially as told to children

fight for (your) life- to make a great effort to stay alive, especially when you are badly injured or seriously ill A young cyclist is fighting for his life after the accident.

for dear life, for your life- as hard or as fast as possible She was holding on to the rope for dear life. Run for your life!

for the life of you (informal)-however hard you try I cannot for the life of me imagine why they want to leave.

full of life- having a lot of energy

get a life (informal)-used to tell someone to stop being boring and to do something more interesting Do us all a favor... get a life!

have nine lives- (especially of a cat) to be very lucky in dangerous situations

have the time of your life (informal) to enjoy yourself very much

in fear of/for your life-feeling frightened that you might be killed

(as) large as life (humorous)-used to show surprise at seeing someone or something I turned around and there was my favorite movie actor standing right next to me, (as) large as life.

larger than life-looking or behaving in a way that is more interesting or exciting than other people, and so is likely to attract attention He's a larger-than-life character.

lay down your life (for somebody/something) (literary)- to die in order to save someone or something SACRIFICE YOURSELF They were prepared to lay down their lives for their country.

lead/live the life of Riley (old-fashioned) (often disapproving)-to live an enjoyable and comfortable life with no problems or responsibilities The two crooks had been living the life of Riley. He planned to retire early and then lead the life of Riley.

a (new) lease on life-the chance to live or last longer, or with a better quality of life Since her hip operation she has a new lease on life.

life after death-the possibility or belief that people continue to exist in some form after they die *Do you believe in life after death?*

life is cheap (*disapproving*)-used to say that there is a situation in which it is not thought to be important if people somewhere die or are treated badly

(have) a life of its own-(of an object) seeming to move or function by itself without a person touching or working it

the life of the party-the most amusing and interesting person at a party, etc.

life's too short (*informal*)-used to say that it is not worth wasting time doing something that you dislike or that is not important

the light of somebody's life-the person someone loves more than any other

make life difficult (for somebody)-to cause problems for someone *She does everything she can to make life difficult for him.*

make somebody's life a misery-to behave in a way that makes someone else feel very unhappy

the man/woman in your life (*informal*)-the man or woman that you are having a sexual or romantic relationship with *Anna has a new man in her life.*

a matter of life and death-used to describe a situation that is very important or serious

not be able to do something to save your life (*informal*)-to be completely unable to do something *He can't interview people to save his life.*

not on your life (*informal*)-used to refuse very firmly to do something

risk life and limb, risk your neck-to risk being killed or injured in order to do something *She risked life and limb to save her children from the fire.*

scare/frighten the life out of somebody-to frighten someone very much *You scared the life out of me coming in so suddenly like that.*

a slice of life-a movie, play, or book that gives a very realistic view of ordinary life

spring into action, spring into/to life (of a person, machine, etc.) to suddenly start working or doing something *"Let's go!" he said, springing into action. The town springs into life (= becomes busy) during the carnival.*

the staff of life (*literary*)-a basic food, especially bread

take somebody's life-to kill someone

take your (own) life-to kill yourself

take your life in your hands-to risk being killed *You take your life in your hands just crossing the street here.*

that's life (*informal*)-used when you are disappointed about something but know that you must accept it *It's a shame I can't go on the trip, but that's life.*

that's the story of my life (*informal*)-when you say that's the story of my life about an unfortunate experience you have had, you mean you have had many similar experiences *Another missed opportunity—that's the story of my life!*

true to life-(of a book, movie, etc.) seeming real rather than invented *I don't think the characters are very true to life.*

variety is the spice of life (*saying*)-new and exciting experiences make life more interesting

walk of life-a person's job or position in society

She has friends from all walks of life.

a/the/somebody's way of life-the typical pattern of behavior of a person or group *the American way of life*

where there's life (, there's hope) (*saying*)-in a bad situation you must not give up hope because there is always a chance that it will improve

you can bet your life/your bottom dollar (on something/(that)...) (informal) used to say that you are certain that something will happen *You can bet your bottom dollar that he'll be late[6]*

CONCLUSION

As we have seen above we could see similarities and dissimilarities of the concept “Life”. In both languages we were able to analyse using the concept “Life” equivalents and their using in Languages.

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